

Energy-Efficient Service Differentiation in Hybrid WiFi/LiFi Networks with Multi-Access Technology Real-Time Intelligent Controller

Asim Ihsan¹, Iman Tavakkolnia¹, and Harald Haas¹

10.5281/zenodo.14613906

¹ LiFi Research and Development Centre (LRDC), Electrical Engineering Division, Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK

Outline

LiFi
Research and
Development
Centre

- 1 **REASON Project.**
- 2 **Objectives.**
- 3 **Proposed Solutions.**
- 4 **Numerical Results.**
- 5 **Conclusions.**

REASON PROJECT

- REASON stands for Realizing Enabling Architectures and Solutions for Open Networks.

Objectives :

- Develop a roadmap for Open 6G networks.
- Integration and Intelligent control of diverse access technologies through mATRIC.
- Drive network densification and performance improvements.
- AI-driven automation for edge and network-wide optimization.
- Cognitive orchestration tools for end-to-end service optimization.

REASON PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Source:

<https://reason-open-networks.ac.uk/>

<https://www.bristol.ac.uk/engineering/research/smart/projects/reason/>

Objectives

- Energy Efficiency.
- Service Differentiation.

Service Differentiation:

- Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC).
 - **Low latency and High Reliability.**
- Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB).
 - **High Capacity.**
- Massive Machine Type Communication (mMTC).
 - **High Density Connectivity.**

Solution:

- Predict and Optimize Algorithm.

LiFi
Research and
Development
Centre

System Model

Stage 1: Prediction of Network Slice

Stage 1: Network Slice Prediction / Selection

- Data Collection from devices and network .
- Collected KPIs includes
 1. Latency.
 2. Reliability.
 3. Temporal information.
 4. Technology supported.
- Non-RT RICs are responsible for training models using historical data based on Resilient back propagation algorithm.
- The trained model then provide network slice prediction in real time through mATRIC.

Figure 1

Stage 2: Energy Efficiency Maximization

$$\text{P1: } \max_{f^{\text{WiFi}}, f^{\text{LiFi}}} \text{EE}^{\text{Hybrid}} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K R_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} + \sum_{k=1}^K R_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}}}{P_{\text{WiFi}} + P_{\text{LiFi}}}$$

$$s \in \{e\text{MBB}, \text{URLLC}, m\text{MTC}\}.$$

Subject to:

$$\text{C1: } R_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} + R_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}} \geq R_{k,s}^{\text{min}}, \quad \forall k,$$

$$\text{C2: } P_{\text{WiFi}} + P_{\text{LiFi}} \leq P_{\text{max}}^{\text{Hybrid}},$$

$$\text{C3: } \sum_{k=1}^K |f_{l,k,s}^{\text{LiFi}}| \leq \min(x_{DC,l}^s, I_{\text{max},s} - x_{DC,l}^s), \quad \forall l,$$

$$\text{C4: } T_{k,s} \leq T_{k,s}^{\text{max}}, \quad \forall k.$$

- **Objective:** Optimize energy efficiency (EE) of hybrid network ensuring service differentiation.
- **Techniques:**
 - Sequential convex approximation.
 - Inner approximation.
- **Approach:**
 - Convert non-convex functions and constraints to convex forms.
 - Developed iterative algorithm for sub-optimal solutions.

$$P_{\text{LiFi}} = \frac{1}{\eta^{\text{LiFi}}} \sum_{k=1}^K \|f_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}}\|^2 \quad P_{\text{WiFi}} = \frac{1}{\eta^{\text{WiFi}}} \sum_{k=1}^K \|f_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}}\|^2 \quad \eta^{\text{LiFi}}, \eta^{\text{WiFi}} \in [0, 1]$$

Stage 2: Energy Efficiency Maximization

$$EE^{\text{Hybrid}} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K R_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} + \sum_{k=1}^K R_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}}}{P_{\text{WiFi}} + P_{\text{LiFi}}}, \quad s \in \{e\text{MBB}, \text{URLLC}, m\text{MTC}\}.$$

For eMBB:

- Since no closed-form expression for LiFi channel capacity.
- We use lower bound from [1] to approximate data rates

$$R_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}} = \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \text{BW}_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}} \ln \left(1 + \frac{e}{2\pi} \gamma_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}} \right)}_{S_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}}} \text{ nats/sec},$$

- While achievable rates for WiFi can be given as

$$R_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} = \underbrace{\text{BW}_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} \ln \left(1 + \gamma_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} \right)}_{S_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}}} \text{ nats/sec}.$$

[1] J.-B. Wang, Q.-S. Hu, J. Wang, M. Chen, and J.-Y. Wang, "Tight bounds on channel capacity for dimmable visible light communications," *J. Lightw. Technol.*, vol. 31, no. 23, pp. 3771–3779, Dec. 1, 2013.

Stage 2: Energy Efficiency Maximization

For URLLC and mMTC [2]:

$$R_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}} = \frac{1}{2} \text{BW}_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}} \left\{ \underbrace{\ln \left(1 + \frac{e}{2\pi} \gamma_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}} \right)}_{S_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}}} - \underbrace{Q^{-1}(\epsilon) \sqrt{\frac{0.5 D_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}}}{L_k}}}_{V_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}}} \right\} \text{ nats/sec,} \quad [3,4]$$

$$R_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} = \text{BW}_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} \left\{ \underbrace{\ln \left(1 + \gamma_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} \right)}_{S_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}}} - \underbrace{Q^{-1}(\epsilon) \sqrt{\frac{D_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}}}{L_k}}}_{V_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}}} \right\} \text{ nats/sec,}$$

$$D_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}} = 1 - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{e}{2\pi} \gamma_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}} \right)^2} \quad \gamma_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}} = \frac{X_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}}}{Y_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}}} = \frac{\left| (\mathbf{h}_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}})^\top \mathbf{f}_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}} \right|^2}{\sum_{j \neq k} \left| (\mathbf{h}_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}})^\top \mathbf{f}_{j,s}^{\text{LiFi}} \right|^2 + (\sigma_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}})^2} \quad \mathbf{f}_{k,s}^{\text{LiFi}} = [f_{1,k,s}^{\text{LiFi}}, f_{2,k,s}^{\text{LiFi}}, \dots, f_{L,k,s}^{\text{LiFi}}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}_+^{L \times 1}$$

$$D_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} = 1 - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \gamma_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} \right)^2} \quad \gamma_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} = \frac{X_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}}}{Y_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}}} = \frac{\left| (\mathbf{h}_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}})^H \mathbf{f}_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} \right|^2}{\sum_{j \neq k} \left| (\mathbf{h}_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}})^H \mathbf{f}_{j,s}^{\text{WiFi}} \right|^2 + (\sigma_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}})^2} \quad \mathbf{f}_{k,s}^{\text{WiFi}} = [f_{1,k,s}^{\text{WiFi}}, f_{2,k,s}^{\text{WiFi}}, \dots, f_{M,k,s}^{\text{WiFi}}]^\top \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$$

[2] M. Karbalaee Motalleb, V. Shah-Mansouri, S. Parsaeefard and O. L. Alcaraz López, "Resource Allocation in an Open RAN System Using Network Slicing," in IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 471-485, March 2023.

[3] G. N. Tran and S. Kim, "Performance Analysis of Short Packets in NOMA VLC Systems," in IEEE Access, vol. 10, pp. 6505-6517, 2022.

[4] Y. Polyanskiy, H. V. Poor, and S. Verdú, "Channel coding rate in the finite blocklength regime," IEEE Trans. Inf. Theory, vol. 56, no. 5, pp. 2307-2359, May 2010.

Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value
Room Size	10m × 10m × 5m
Height of Hybrid Transmitters	4(m)
Receiver FOV (ϕ_{FOV})	60°
LED Emission Semiangle ($\psi_{1/2}$)	70°
Area of Photodiode (A_D)	1 cm ²
Photodiode Responsivity	0.54 A/W
LiFi Bandwidth ($BW_{k,s}^{LiFi}$)	20 MHz
WiFi Bandwidth ($BW_{k,s}^{WiFi}$)	10 MHz
Refractive Index (r)	1.5
LiFi Power Amplifier Efficiency (η^{LiFi})	0.5
WiFi Power Amplifier Efficiency (η^{WiFi})	0.5
DC Bias ($x_{DC,l}^s$)	$\sqrt{6}$ A
Maximum Permissible Current ($I_{max,l}$)	5 A
Optical Filter Gain (G_f)	1
PSD of AWGN in LiFi ($\mu_{k,s}^{LiFi}$)	10 ⁻²¹ A ² /Hz
PSD of AWGN in WiFi ($\mu_{k,s}^{WiFi}$)	-174 dbm/Hz

Simulation Parameters

Numerical Results

Figure 2

M=Number of antennas at the WiFi Transmitter.

L=Number of LEDs at the LiFi Transmitter.

Figure 3

ZF = Zero-forcing precoding.

MRT= Maximum Ratio Transmission precoding.

Numerical Results

Figure 4

Conclusions

- It addresses the gap in integrating service differentiation with energy efficiency in hybrid WiFi/LiFi networks.
- Hybrid WiFi/LiFi system outperforms WiFi-only systems with our proposed predict and optimize algorithm.
- Our approach outperforms conventional ZF and MRT precoding methods, showing better energy efficiency.

LiFi
Research and
Development
Centre

Thank
you!!

QUESTIONS ARE WELCOMED